

Securing Organization’s Data - A Role-Based Authorized Keyword Search Scheme with Efficient Decryption

K.Rama Krishna, Veeranki Sri Harsha, Koppuravuri Rajkumar, Shaik Mastan, Pallepati Rakshan Kumar

Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Chalapathi Institute of Technology, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India.

To Cite this Article

K.Rama Krishna, Veeranki Sri Harsha, Koppuravuri Rajkumar, Shaik Mastan & Pallepati Rakshan Kumar (2025). Securing Organization’s Data - A Role-Based Authorized Keyword Search Scheme with Efficient Decryption. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 11(04), 120-127. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15110678>

Article Info

Received: 03 March 2025; Accepted: 28 March 2025.; Published: 31 March 2025.

Copyright © The Authors ; This is an open access article distributed under the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

KEYWORDS

*Role-Based Encryption,
Authorized Users,
Revocation Mechanisms*

ABSTRACT

For better data availability and accessibility while ensuring data secrecy, organizations often tend to outsource their encrypted data to the cloud storage servers, thus bringing the challenge of keyword search over encrypted data. In this paper, we propose a novel authorized keyword search scheme using Role-Based Encryption (RBE) technique in a cloud environment. The contributions of this paper are multi-fold. First, it presents a keyword search scheme which enables only authorized users, having properly assigned roles, to delegate keyword-based data search capabilities over encrypted data to the cloud providers without disclosing any sensitive information. Second, it supports a multi-organization cloud environment, where the users can be associated with more than one organization. Third, the proposed scheme provides efficient decryption, conjunctive keyword search and revocation mechanisms. Fourth, the proposed scheme outsources expensive cryptographic operations in decryption to the cloud in a secure manner. Fifth, we have provided a formal security analysis to prove that the proposed scheme is semantically secure against Chosen Plaintext and Chosen Keyword Attacks. Finally, our performance analysis shows that the proposed scheme is suitable for practical applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

Searchable Encryption (SE) has gained a considerable amount of interest from the research community to

address the issue of searching over encrypted data [1]. It has already been considered as one of the suitable cryptographic techniques that can prevent unauthorized

entities including the cloud service provider from accessing and knowing any useful information about the outsourced sensitive data to the cloud [2]. SE enables the users to delegate data search capabilities for some keywords over the encrypted data to a service provider without disclosing any useful information about the searched keywords and the actual content of the encrypted data. This process is also referred to as keyword search. Typically, in keyword search, data owners outsource their data in an encrypted form along with an encrypted index of keywords. Whenever a user wants to access data, the user sends the desired keywords in the form of trapdoors to the service provider. In return, the service provider uses the trapdoors to perform search over the encrypted indexes and sends the associated encrypted data, if there is a match between the keywords associated with the trapdoor and encrypted indexes. Many works have been done in the area of keyword search, achieving search authorization in a coarse-grained way. That is, the users can search all the keywords using their secret keys [3]. However, this kind of authorization may disclose sensitive information. For example, Organization A outsources its data files to the cloud so that its employees can easily access them. Assume Organization A is a participant in a consortium with another Organization B and other organizations. Suppose, some files are associated with the keywords "Organization B" and "Project X" which are only allowed to be accessed by the Managers in the Organization A. In this case, if an adversary can search for the keywords "Organization B" and "Project X", it can get all the encrypted files associated with these two keywords. This will eventually reveal, without knowing the actual content, that Organization A and Organization B are collaborating on Project X, which may not be desirable. To address this problem, several authorized keyword search schemes have been proposed for multi-user settings using different cryptographic techniques, e.g. Pairing-Based Encryption [4], Predicate Encryption [5] and Attribute-Based Encryption [6], [3], where multiple users are able to perform keyword search operations based on some access policies. However, none of these techniques efficiently support hierarchies in an organization, where higher level authorities can inherit access rights of their subordinates. As such, all these schemes [4], [5], [6], [3] are not able to reflect efficiently organization's policies

and structures [8]. Role-Based Encryption (RBE) [9], [7], [10] is an emerging cryptographic technique, which combines both properties of the traditional Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) [11] and cryptographic encryption methods, to achieve data access control over encrypted data. In RBE, the data owner encrypts data using a RBAC access policy defined over some roles [3], and any user having proper roles can derive the secret keys for decryption. Unlike the traditional RBAC method, RBE enables the data owners to define and enforce RBAC access policies on the encrypted data itself. This, in turn, reduces the dependency of the data owners on untrusted service provider for defining and enforcing access policies while sharing data with other authorized users. Moreover, similar to the RBAC, in RBE, roles can inherit access permissions from other roles [7]. Hence, the roles can be organized in a hierarchical structure. This is one of the main advantages of RBE over other encryption mechanisms such as Attribute-Based Encryption [12], [13], as it can reflect closely a real-world organization's policies and structure. The inheritance property of the RBE makes it more suitable for large scale organizations such as enterprises with complex hierarchical structures [7]. For better illustration, let us consider a sample role hierarchy, shown in Figure 1, of an organization/enterprise based on the designation of the employees. The CEO of the organization supervises many employees such as directors, project leaders, engineers, etc. Similarly, the directors manage project leaders, engineers, and so on. In such scenarios, the higher-level authorities inherit the privileges of its lower-level authorities. As such, in an organization scenario, RBE is the more suitable cryptographic technique (due to its inheritance property) for designing a keyword search mechanism compared with other cryptographic techniques such as the ABE. RBE has been used to provide data access control in cloud environments over encrypted data [7], [10], [8]. However, they mainly focus on a single organization cloud environment scenario, where users can have roles only in a single organization and hence can access data associated with only that organization. In many practical scenarios, the owner of data might wish to have access policies defined over roles across multiple organizations and domains. For example, a data owner might want to share medical records only with the users who have the

role of a doctor issued by a hospital and the role of a clinical researcher issued by a medical laboratory. The data owner can specify a RBAC access policy in such a way that only the users having the access privileges for the roles "Doctor" and "Clinical Researcher" can gain access to the content corresponding to the encrypted data. Similar instances can also happen in enterprises. For example, it may happen that a financial budget document in an organization can only be accessed by a finance officer in the enterprise and a tax officer from an auditing organization. The data owner can choose an access policy that can allow any user having privileges for the roles "Finance Officer" and "Tax Officer" and "Auditing Officer" to access to the financial document. Other examples include the formation of consortiums and collaborations among multiple organizations, where users can hold different roles in the participating organizations. Hence there is a need for designing effective keyword search schemes over encrypted data in the cloud with data coming from multiple organizations, as well as a controlling access to data, both of which are important and topical research problems which need to be addressed.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

This section presents a brief overview of some notable works in the keyword search area, including some cryptographic RBAC based data access control schemes.

2.1 Keyword Search over Encrypted Data

Search over encrypted data has been extensively studied since the past decade. Song et al. presented the first practical symmetric key cryptography based searchable encryption scheme that can search full text over encrypted data [15]. Later, several searchable encryption schemes have been proposed, for various functionalities and security requirements such as conjunctive (or multi) keyword search [6], [16], Rank Keyword Search [17], verifiable keyword search [18], [19], traceable keyword search [20], forward and backward security [21], [22], keyword guessing attack [23], multi authority [24], and so on. Broadly, all the keyword search schemes can be divided into two categories, namely, Sym metric Searchable Encryption (SSE) and Searchable Public Key Encryption (SPKE). The core difference between these two categories is that SSE is based on symmetric key cryptography, while SPKE is based on public key cryptography. Some of the notable SSE schemes are [25],

[21], [26], [27], [22], [28], [29], [30], [31]; while [32], [33], [6], [3], [18], [34], [35], [36], [24] are SPKE. In [25], Curtmola et al. proposed a SSE scheme for multi user settings⁵, which can perform single keyword search. In [26], Kamara et al. proposed a dynamic version of the scheme [25] that can add and delete files at any time efficiently. However, the scheme [26] leaks significant information while performing update operation [29]. To reduce the information leakage, in [21], Stefanov et al. first introduced the forward secrecy⁶ and in [27], Bost et al. introduced back ward secrecy in SSE. Later on, several works such as [22], [28], [31], have been proposed in the direction of forward and backward secrecy in SSE for achieving better security and efficiency. In [30], Liu et al. proposed a keyword search scheme which enables the users to verify the search results against the dishonest servers. Although the SSE schemes provide better efficiency in terms of computation cost, SPKE schemes provide more flexible and expressive search queries [6]. Recently, several SPKE schemes have been proposed using Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE) technique [6], [3], [34], [35], [36], [24], where any user having a qualified set of attributes that satisfy an access policy can perform search operation using some keywords. That is, these schemes provide authorized keyword search, which allows only intended users to do the search in multi-user settings. In [6], Sun et al. proposed keyword search schemes for both single and conjunctive keyword search, which does not introduce any additional overhead in the system. In [3], Hu et al. proposed another ABE based keyword search scheme for dynamic policy update, where the data owners can securely update the access policies using proxy re-encryption and secret sharing techniques. In [34], Miao et al. proposed an ABE based keyword search scheme for hierarchical data, which also supports conjunctive keyword search. In [35], Chaudhari et al. proposed an authorized keyword search scheme using ABE, which hides the access policy from all the intended entities including the public cloud. In [36], Zeng et al. addressed the forward security issue for ABE settings using the concept of 0-Encoding and 1- Encoding. Recently, in [24] Miao et al. proposed a multi-authority ABE based keyword search scheme. Unlike the previous ABE based keyword search schemes such as [6], [3], [34], [35], [36], in [24] a user can hold attributes from more than one Attribute Authorities

(AA). All the aforementioned schemes do not support role hierarchy and inheritance properties.

2.2 Cryptographic RBAC based Data Access Control A cryptographic RBAC based data access control mechanism integrates the traditional RBAC model with cryptographic encryption method to enforce RBAC access policy on encrypted data. It enables the data to be encrypted using RBAC access policy defined over some role(s). Any user, possessing the required role(s) satisfying the associated RBAC access policy is allowed to decrypt the data. Some notable works in this area are [38], [39], [40], [41], [42], [7], [10], [8], where [38], [43], [44], [39], [40], [41], [42] are based on Hierarchical Key Assignment (HKA) method and [7], [10], [8] are based on RBE method. Access control using HKA method has been studied in the early 1980s. In [38], Akl et al. presented the first cryptographic hierarchical access control technique to solve the hierarchical multi-level security problem, where authorized users are allowed to possess different access privileges. The users are grouped into disjoint sets (or classes) and form a hierarchical structure of classes. Each class is assigned with a unique encryption key and a public parameter in such a way that a higher-level class can derive encryption keys of any lower-level classes using its own encryption key and some public parameters. Later on, several other hierarchical access control schemes have been proposed using different techniques, e.g. [43], [44], [39], [40], [41], [42]. However, the main drawback of the HKA schemes is the high complexity in setting up the encryption keys for a large set of users [7]. Also, the user revocation is a challenging task, as all the encryption keys that are known to the revoked users, and their related public parameters need to be updated per user revocation, which may incur a high overhead on the system. In [7], Zhou et al. proposed the first RBE scheme for channel such as SSL (Secure Sockets Layer) respectively. It comprises five entities, namely, System Authorities, Role Managers, Data Owners, Users, and Public Cloud having the following responsibilities: Public parameters System Authority (SA): Each organization has one SA, which maintains the role hierarchy of that organization. It generates system public parameters and master secrets for the organization. SA also maintains all the role-managers that are associated with the organization, and it issues secret keys for each role manager. In addition, SA issues private and public

keys for all the registered users. Further, it issues private, public and proxy re-encryption keys to the public cloud. Moreover, SA is responsible for revoking users from the system when needed. Proxy re-encryption, private keys Role-Manager (RM): It is an entity of an organization which manages the role(s). Note that, the roles are assigned by the SA. In addition, it also issues and manages role-keys for the users. Data Owners (owners): It is an entity who owns the data and wants to outsource his/her data to the public cloud. An owner first encrypts data using a RBAC access policy before outsourcing to the public cloud. The owner first encrypts a plaintext data using a random sceretkey by following any secure symmetric key encryption algorithm, e.g., Advanced Encryption Standard (AES). Afterward, the owner chooses a set of keywords associated with the plaintext data and encrypts those keywords along with the random key using the chosen RBAC access policy. The owner then combines all the cipher texts into one archive and outsources it to the cloud storage servers. Secrets data sharing in an untrusted hybrid cloud environment. In [7], the cipher texts and secret keys of the users are constant in size. This scheme also offers user revocation capability. In [10], Zhu et al. proposed another RBE scheme. In this scheme, the cipher text size linearly increases with the number of roles. Recently, in [8], Perez et al. proposed a data-centric RBAC based data access control mechanism for cloud storage systems using the concept of proxy re encryption and identity-based encryption techniques. To share data with the authorized users, the data owner generates proxy re-encryption keys based on some RBAC access policies and keep the re-encryption keys along with the cipher texts in the cloud storage servers. When an authorized user accesses the cipher text, the service provider re-encrypts the cipher text using the proxy re-encryption keys based on a RBAC access policy. However, none of [7], [10], [8] address keyword search functionality. Also these schemes do not support multi organization cloud storage systems, where a user can possess roles from more than one organization.

3. EXISTINGSYSTEM

Data search over encrypted data has been extensively studied since the past decade. Song et al. presented the first practical symmetric key cryptography based searchable encryption scheme that can search full text

over encrypted data [15]. Later, several searchable encryption schemes have been proposed, for various functionalities and security requirements such as conjunctive (or multi) keyword search, Rank Keyword Search, verifiable keyword search, traceable keyword search [20], forward and backward security, keyword guessing attack [23], multi authority [24], and so on. Broadly, all the keyword search schemes can be divided into two categories, namely, Symmetric Searchable Encryption (SSE) and Searchable Public Key Encryption (SPKE). The core difference between these two categories is that SSE is based on symmetric key cryptography, while SPKE is based on public key cryptography. Some of the notable SSE schemes are SPKE. In [25], Curtmola et al. proposed a SSE scheme for multiuser settings⁵, which can perform single keyword search. In [26], Kamara et al. proposed a dynamic version of the scheme [25] that can add and delete files at any time efficiently. However, the scheme [26] leaks significant information while performing update operation [29]. To reduce the information leakage, in [21], Stefanov et al. first introduced the forward secrecy⁶ and in [27], Bost et al. introduced backward secrecy in SSE. Later on, several works have been proposed in the direction of forward and backward secrecy in SSE for achieving better security and efficiency. In [30], Liu et al. proposed a keyword search scheme which enables the users to verify the search results against the dishonest servers. Although the SSE schemes provide better efficiency in terms of computation cost, SPKE schemes provide more flexible and expressive search queries.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Our main contribution in this paper is that we propose an authorized keyword search scheme over encrypted data for multi-organization settings using a novel Role-Based Encryption (RBE) technique. That is, our scheme enables keyword search over encrypted data, which is an authorized search in the sense that only users having authorized roles are allowed to perform keyword search on encrypted data stored in the cloud coming from data owners in different organizations. Furthermore, it allows the authorized users the ability to decrypt. In addition, we have presented an efficient user revocation and conjunctive keyword search mechanisms for the proposed scheme. Our scheme fills the research gaps in the areas of searchable encryption and in RBE.

The existing RBE schemes only support single organization environment, whereas our scheme enables the users to be part of more than one organization and to hold roles from these organizations simultaneously (such as in a consortium or collaborative projects).

The main technical results in this paper are as follows:

- 1) We develop a novel RBE scheme that enables the organizations to outsource their encrypted data in an untrusted public cloud. The RBE scheme is designed in such a way that any user possessing roles associated with the defined RBAC access policy or any higher-level roles in the hierarchy (due to the inheritance property) can delegate keyword search capabilities over encrypted data to the public cloud along with the ability to decrypt. Most importantly, our designed RBE scheme enables the data owners to define and enforce RBAC access policies in the encrypted data itself, thereby data owners retain full control over their outsourced data.
- 2) Our scheme also addresses the data access control issue in a multi-organization cloud environment in RBE settings, and is the first doing so, to the best of our knowledge. Our scheme enables the users to hold roles from more than one organization. As such, a data owner can define RBAC access policy with the roles from more than one organization and can enforce it in the encrypted data itself so that any user holding the qualified roles can get access.
- 3) We introduce a conjunctive keyword search⁴ mechanism with minimal overhead in the system along with a privilege revocation technique.
- 4) We have provided a formal security analysis of our scheme to demonstrate its security against the Chosen Plaintext Attacks and the Chosen Keyword Attacks.
- 5) Moreover, our scheme presents a comprehensive performance analysis, which shows that it is sufficiently efficient to be used in practical applications.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig 1: System Architecture

5. UML DIAGRAMS

1. CLASS DIAGRAM

The cornerstone of event-driven data exploration is the class outline. Both broad practical verification of the application's precision and fine-grained demonstration of the model translation into software code rely on its availability. Class graphs are another data visualization option.

The core components, application involvement, and class changes are all represented by comparable classes in the class diagram. Classes with three-participant boxes are referred to be "incorporated into the framework," and each class has three different locations:

- The techniques or actions that the class may use or reject are depicted at the bottom.

Fig 5.1 shows the class diagram

2. USECASE DIAGRAM:

A use case diagram in the Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a type of behavioral diagram defined by and created from a Use-case analysis. Its purpose is to present a graphical overview of the functionality provided by a system in terms of actors, their goals (represented as use cases), and any dependencies between those use cases. The main purpose of a use case diagram is to show what system functions are performed for which actor. Roles of the actors in the system can be depicted.

Fig 5.2 Shows the Use case Diagram

3. SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

A sequence diagram in Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a kind of interaction diagram that shows how processes operate with one another and in what order. It is a construct of a Message Sequence Chart. Sequence diagrams are sometimes called event diagrams, event scenarios, and timing diagrams.

Fig 5.3 Shows the Sequence Diagram

6. RESULTS

6.1 Output Screens

Fig 6.1 User Login Page

In above screen shows the Login page of the User.

Fig 6.2 View and authorize owners

In above screen shows the View and Authorize owners.

Fig 6.3 Request Secret Key

In above screen shows the request for the secret key.

Fig 6.4 Upload the file

In above screen show the uploading file.

Fig 6.5 View all Uploaded files.

In above screen shows all files uploaded by the users.

Fig 6.6 Search Query Document.

In above screen shows searching the query document.

Fig 6.7 View File Rank Results in Bar Chart.

In above screen shows the view file rank results in bar chart.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper has proposed a novel authorized keyword search mechanism with efficient decryption using the RBE technique for a cloud environment, where multiple organizations can outsource their sensitive data. The proposed scheme enables the owners to define and enforce RBAC access policies on the encrypted data, thereby avoiding reducing the dependency on the service provider. It also enables the public cloud to authenticate the users first before performing computationally expensive search operations, which reduces overhead on the system. In addition, the proposed scheme helps to prevent replay attacks.

Conjunctive keyword search is supported without introducing any significant overhead into the system. Further, the complete and role-level user revocation mechanisms are supported for revoking access privileges of the users in both organization level and role level respectively. Moreover, an outsourced decryption mechanism is introduced in the proposed scheme to reduce decryption processing cost at the end-user side, which makes it suitable for resource constrained environment. Furthermore, we have formally proved that the proposed scheme provides provable security against Chosen Plaintext and Chosen Keyword Attacks. Our performance analysis shows that the proposed scheme is suitable for real-world applications in terms of computation, communication and storage overhead. This paper has introduced a new direction in designing a searchable encryption mechanism using the RBE technique. Further works include improving the efficiency of role-level revocation of RBE based keyword search schemes as well as for dynamic addition (removal) of roles into (from) a role hierarchy.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Han, J. Qin, and J. Hu. "secure searches in the cloud: A survey". *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 62:66 – 75, 2016.
- [2] C. B'osch et al. A Survey of Provably Secure Searchable Encryption. *ACM Comput. Surv.*, 47(2):18:1–18:51, Aug. 2014.
- [3] B. Hu et al. DABKS: Dynamic attribute-based keyword search in cloud computing. In *Proc.of the 2017 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*, pages 1–6, May 2017.
- [4] F. Bao et al. Private Query on Encrypted Data in Multi-user Settings. In *Proc.of the 4th International Conference on Information Security Practice and Experience, ISPEC'08*, pages 71–85, 2008.
- [5] M. Li et al. Authorized Private Keyword Search over Encrypted Data in Cloud Computing. In *2011 31st International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems*, pages 383–392, June 2011.
- [6] Kumar, K. K., Kumar, S. G. B., Rao, S. G. R., & Sydulu, S. S. J. (2017, November). Safe and high secured ranked keyword search over an outsourced cloud data. In *2017 International Conference on Inventive Computing and Informatics (ICICI)* (pp. 20-25). IEEE.
- [7] Kommineni, K. K., Pilli, R. B., Tejaswi, K., & Siva, P. V. (2023). Attention-based Bayesian inferential imagery captioning maker. *Materials Today: Proceedings*.
- [8] Kommineni, K.K., Prasad, A. Enhancing Data Security and Privacy in SDN-Enabled MANETs Through Improved Data Aggregation Protection and Secrecy. *Wireless Pers Commun* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11277-024-11635-w>
- [9] Kommineni, K. K. , & Prasad, A. . (2023). A Review on Privacy and Security Improvement Mechanisms in MANETs. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering*, 12(2), 90–99. Retrieved from <https://ijisae.org/index.php/IJISAE/article/view/4224>
- [10] Sreechandra Swarna and Venkata Ratnam Kolluru (2024), Active Channel Selection by Sensors using Artificial Neural Networks. *IJEER* 12(4), 1466-1473. DOI: 10.37391/ijeer.120441.
- [11] Kumar, M. S., Vellela, S. S., Rao, G. R., Srinivas, B. R., Javvadi, S., SyamsundaraRao, T., & Kumar, K. K. (2024, September). An Interactive Healthcare Recommendation System Using Big Data Analytics. In *2024 3rd International Conference for Advancement in Technology (ICONAT)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [12] Addepalli, T., Babu, K. J., Beno, A., Potti, B. M. K., Sundari, D. T., & Devana, V. K. R. (2022). Characteristic mode analysis of two port semi-circular arc-shaped multiple-input-multiple-output antenna with high isolation for 5G sub-6 GHz and wireless local area network applications. *International Journal of Communication Systems*, 35(14), e5257.
- [13] Srija, V., & Krishna, P. B. M. (2015). Implementation of agricultural automation system using web & gsm technologies. *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*, 4(09), 385-389.
- [14] Potti, B., Subramanyam, M. V., & Prasad, K. S. (2013). A packet priority approach to mitigate starvation in wireless mesh network with multimedia traffic. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 62(14).
- [15] Potti, B., Subramanyam, M. V., & Satya Prasad, K. (2016). Adopting Multi-radio Channel Approach in TCP Congestion Control Mechanisms to Mitigate Starvation in Wireless Mesh Networks. In *Information Science and Applications (ICISA) 2016* (pp. 85-95). Springer Singapore.
- [16] Vellela, S. S., & Balamanigandan, R. (2024). Optimized clustering routing framework to maintain the optimal energy status in the wsn mobile cloud environment. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 83(3), 7919-7938.
- [17] Vellela, S. S., & Balamanigandan, R. (2022, December). Design of Hybrid Authentication Protocol for High Secure Applications in Cloud Environments. In *2022 International Conference on Automation, Computing and Renewable Systems (ICACRS)* (pp. 408-414). IEEE.
- [18] Vellela, S. S., & Balamanigandan, R. (2023). An intelligent sleep-awake energy management system for wireless sensor network. *Peer-to-Peer Networking and Applications*, 16(6), 2714-2731.
- [19] Vellela, S. S., Balamanigandan, R., & Praveen, S. P. (2022). Strategic Survey on Security and Privacy Methods of Cloud Computing Environment. *Journal of Next Generation Technology*, 2(1).
- [20] Vellela, S. S., & Balamanigandan, R. (2024). An efficient attack detection and prevention approach for secure WSN mobile cloud environment. *Soft Computing*, 28(19), 11279-11293.
- [21] Polasi, P. K., Vellela, S. S., Narayana, J. L., Simon, J., Kapileswar, N., Prabu, R. T., & Rashed, A. N. Z. (2024). Data rates transmission, operation performance speed and figure of merit signature for various quadrature light sources under spectral and thermal effects. *Journal of Optics*, 1-11.